

EARTH SCIENCES

THE BASIC THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING THE ENVIRONMENTAL SITUATION ON PLANET EARTH. BRIEF OPINION

Azizov I.

*Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnologies Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences,
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Tsygankova V.

Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

ABSTRACT

Environmental problems are one of the basic global threats of the international security now. The basic environmental problems are reduction of an ozone layer, global warming, pollution of an atmosphere, greenhouse effect, and pollution of World Ocean, pollution of soil, reduction of plant productivity, food crisis, and reduction of variety of the biological kinds living on the Earth. In present article the reasons, consequences and approaches to the decision of these problems are considered.

Keywords: reduction of an ozone cloud, pollution of an atmosphere, climatic changes, greenhouse effect, pollution of World Ocean, soil pollution, plant diseases, reduction of plant productivity, food crisis; reduction of variety of the biological kinds living on the Earth.

First, it should be noted that there were about ten civilizations before us. According to theories, ancient civilizations disappeared for various reasons: due to a planetary catastrophe - an impact from space; due to the release of the unknown nature of energies in the form of a cosmic ray descending many times a year; due to crazy wars between states. We live on a ball called planet Earth. The earth we live on moves at a speed of 30 km/sec. Each planet, including the Earth, has a certain capacity. According to Kepler's laws [1], planets can revolve around a star indefinitely, however, due to deviations from these laws, an instability variant is also possible when the planets leave their orbit or, conversely, fall inside the star. When rebooting, it can go beyond its orbit, which can be accompanied by anomalies that have a detrimental effect on living things. We are currently witnessing global changes taking place on our planet. These anomalies include climatic changes,

elevated level of ozone, temperature extremes, drought, soil salinity and pollution by industrial waste and heavy metals, as well as the spread of pathogenic fungi, parasitic nematodes and insects that cause plant diseases and reduced plant productivity [2 - 9] leading to a food crisis, rising sea levels, new diseases and the pandemic.

In addition to this, crazy wars between states for the capture of new territories of the Earth with the use of explosive rockets. The explosion products have a detrimental effect on the civilian population and the ozone layer of the atmosphere, which protects the Earth's biota from the harmful effects of ultraviolet radiation. The destruction of the ozone layer is the death of the living beings of the Earth. Every thinking person is concerned about the current situation and thinks about the future generation. In this situation, we, people of science and scientists, have a great responsibility.

The destruction of forested areas is taking place all over the planet and even affects parks and protected areas, which are the main supplier of oxygen to the planet. Acid rain also causes considerable damage to

the flora, which is caused by various enterprises, mostly metallurgical plants. During their activities, they pollute the atmosphere with sulfur and nitrogen oxides.

Industrial waste also harms rivers, lakes and other bodies of water. In many parts of the world, the water is undrinkable. Each year more than 26 million tons of oil products, a huge number of non-biodegradable sub-

stances, and products of the chemical and military industries enter the world's oceans. This in turn affects marine life.

About 30 kilometers from Earth is a thin layer that absorbs ultraviolet rays. It gives us protection against many skin diseases, including cancer. The ozone layer is destroyed by freon-based aerosols, aircraft and

spacecraft engines. Further destruction of this layer could dramatically alter the planet's climate. Biological diversity is a variety of forms and processes.

Biodiversity matters for the development of new medical products, as well as for the development industry, the creation of such problems, like rubber containing starches, fats and oils, as well as natural and chemical pesticides and fungicides [10 - 12]. Due to global deterioration natural environment, the disappearance of animal and plant species occurs is going at a very fast pace. This especially applies to this various types of animals and plants of the ecosystem, like tropical forests, coral reefs and wetlands.

Is it possible to find ways to save humanity from more serious anomalies?

We are very concerned about the fate of our civilization and we can offer the ways to save humanity on the planet Earth which are outlined in our published works [2, 8, 9, 13 - 31] and set out in our basic theoretical principles dedicated to the preservation of life on our planet Earth. We propose to convene a worldwide symposium with the participation of smart leaders and leading scientists from all countries and discuss the issues:

1. To prepare a law on fertility and mortality in the modern world, contributing to the preservation of the population at a stable level;

2. Prohibit the production of heavy weapons and means of mass destruction of people, including research on the creation of new artificial viruses and bacteria that contribute to the mass destruction of the Earth's population, leading ultimately to the death of modern civilization. Ensure peaceful, friendly coexistence of all states and peoples on the planet;

3. Preserve biodiversity on the planet; neutralize hazardous wastes and gases that pollute nature;

4. Set scientists the task of creating new varieties of agricultural plants that are resistant to drought, salinity, high and low temperatures and radiation;

5. Economically use water, mineral fertilizers, to create new ways of rational use of the intensity and spectral composition of sunlight;

6. Increasing soil fertility. Breeding new plant varieties with genetically improved adaptive abilities to abiotic and biotic stress factors and application of new plant growing technologies using environmentally friendly biostimulants and plant growth regulators to

protect plants from biotic and abiotic stresses and to prevent a decrease in plant productivity and food crisis; use of green energy power plants will minimize environmental pollution.

The solution to these global problems will contribute to improving the environmental situation on planet Earth.

References

- Johannes Kepler: His Life, His Laws and Times | NASA". Archived from the original on 24 June 2021. Retrieved 1 September 2023.
- Ibrahim Azizov. Drought, salinization, radiation: how to protect plants from their influence. 2016. Germany. "LAMBERT". 80 p. (in Rus.).
- Anderson R., Bayer P.E., and Edwards D. Climate change and the need for agricultural adaptation. *Current opinion in plant biology*. 2020. 56: 197-202. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32057694/>.
- Fahad S., Bajwa A. A., Nazir U., Anjum S. A., Farooq A., Zohaib A., Sadia S., Nasim W., Adkins S., Saud S., Ihsan M. Z., Alharby H., Wu C., Wang D., & Huang J. Crop Production under Drought and Heat Stress: Plant Responses and Management Options. *Frontiers in plant science*. 2017. 8: 1147. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.01147>.
- Rejeb I.B., Pastor V. and Mauch-Mani B. Plant Responses to Simultaneous Biotic and Abiotic Stress: Molecular Mechanisms. *Plants*. 2014. 3: 458-475. <https://www.mdpi.com/2223-7747/3/4/458>.
- Dresselhaus, T., and Hückelhoven R. Biotic and Abiotic Stress Responses in Crop Plants. *Agronomy*. 2018. 8: 267. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4395/8/11/267>.
- Gimenez E., Salinas M. and Manzano-Agugliaro F. Worldwide Research on Plant Defense against Biotic Stresses as Improvement for Sustainable Agriculture. *Sustainability*. 2018. 10: 391. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/10/2/391>.
- Tsygankova V.A., Blyuss K.B., Shysha E.N., Biliavska L.A., Iutynska G.A., Andrusevich Ya.V., Ponomarenko S.P., Yemets A.I. and Blume Ya.B. Using Microbial Biostimulants to Deliver RNA Interference in Plants as an Effective Tool for Biocontrol of Pathogenic Fungi, Parasitic Nematodes and Insects. Chapter 6. P. 205-319. In: "Research Advances in Plant biotechnology". **Series:** Plant Science Research and Practices / Ed. Ya.B. Blume. USA: Nova Science Publishers, Inc., 2020, 270 p. URL: <https://novapublishers.com/shop/research-advances-in-plant-biotechnology>.
- Tsygankova V.A., Spivak S.I., Shysha E.N., Pastukhova N.L., Biliavska L.A., Iutynska G.A., Kyrylenko V.M., Yemets A.I., Blume Ya.B. The role of polycomponent biostimulants in increasing plant resistance to the biotic and abiotic stress factors. Pp. 1–86. Chapter 1. In: *Agricultural Research Updates*. Vol. 46. Editor(s): **Prathamesh Gorawala and Srushti Mandhatri**. Nova Science Publishers, Inc., NY, USA. 2023, 307 p. <https://novapublishers.com/shop/agricultural-research-updates-volume-46/>.
- Alewu B. and Nosiri C. Pesticides and Human Health, *Pesticides in the Modern World - Effects of Pesticides Exposure*. M. Stoytcheva (Ed.), InTechOpen. 2011. 390 p. <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/19601>.
- Nicolopoulou-Stamati P., Maipas S., Kotampasi C., Stamatis P., Hens L. Chemical Pesticides and Human Health: The Urgent Need for a New Concept in Agriculture. *Front Public Health*. 2016. 4: Article 148. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4947579/>
- Goswami S.K., Singh V., Chakdar H., Choudhary P. Harmful effects of fungicides - current status. *Inter J Agric Environ Biotech*. 2018. 1025-1033. https://www.academia.edu/74045392/Harmful_Effects_of_Fungicides_Current_Status.
- Aliyeva N.Z., Tagiyeva K.R., Mamedov Z.M., Azizov I.V. Effect of iron oxide nanoparticles on the growth of maize sprouts cultivated under drought stress and on the activity dynamics of NADP-ISDH enzyme /*Advanced Studies in Biology*, Vol. 15, 2023, no. 1-P.149-157. (WOS).
- Ismayilova G.H., Azizov I.V. Influence of Ti, Zn and Fe oxide nanoparticles on seed germination capability, photosynthetic pigment content and activity of photosystem II *Triticum aestivum* L. /*Advanced Studies in Biology*, Vol. 15, 2023, no. 1-P.157-165.(WOS).
- Olatunbosun A, Nigar H, Rovshan K, Nurlan A, Boyukhanim J, Narmina A, Ibrahim A. Comparative impact of nanoparticles on salt resistance of wheat plants. *MethodsX*. 2023; 11: 102371. doi: 10.1016/j.mex.2023.102371.
- Kanishova M.A., Tagieva K.R., Azizov I.V. Influence of sodium chloride on morphophysiological characteristics of wheat and maize plants. In: *Factori Experimentolnoy evolyusii organizmov*. 2023. V.33. P.75-78.
- Shamilov E.N., Abdullayev A.S., Shamilli V.E., Farajov M.F., Azizov I.V., HaliyevK.A., Jalilova A.A. Citogenetic changes in irradiated rats under influence of guaninum-zinc chloride complex.In: *Factori Experimentolnoy evolyusii organizmov*. 2023. V.33. P. 187-192.
- Blyuss K.B., Fatehi F., Tsygankova V.A., Biliavska L.O., Iutynska G.O., Yemets A.I., Blume Y.B. RNAi-based biocontrol of wheat nematodes using natural poly-component biostimulants. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 2019. 10: 483. doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00483.
- Tsygankova V.A., Andrusevich Ya.V., Shtompel O.I., Solomyanny R. M., Hurenko A.O., Frasinuk M.S., Mrug G.P., Shablykin O.V., Pilyo S.G., Kornienko A.M. & Brovarets V. S. New Auxin and Cytokinin Related Compounds Based on Synthetic Low Molecular Weight Heterocycles, Chapter 16, In: Aftab T. (Ed.) *Auxins, Cytokinins and Gibberellins Signaling in Plants, Signaling and Communication in Plants*, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, 2022. 353-377. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-05427-3_16.
- Pidlisnyuk V., Mamirova A., Newton R. A., Stefanovska T., Zhukov O., Tsygankova V., and

- Shapoval P. The role of plant growth regulators in *Miscanthus* × *giganteus* utilisation on soils contaminated with trace elements. *Agronomy*. 2022. 12(12): 2999. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12122999>.
21. Tsygankova V.A., Voloshchuk I.V., Kopich V.M., Pilyo S.G., Klyuchko S. V., Brovarets V.S. Studying the effect of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur on growth and productivity of sunflower. *Journal of Advances in Agriculture*. 2023. 14: 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.24297/jaa.v14i.9453>.
22. Tsygankova V.A., Voloshchuk I.V., Pilyo S.H., Klyuchko S.V., Brovarets V.S. Enhancing Sorghum Productivity with Methyur, Kamethur, and Ivin Plant Growth Regulators. *Biology and Life Sciences Forum*. 2023. 27(1): 36. <https://doi.org/10.3390/IECAG2023-15222>.
23. Tsygankova V.A., Andrushevich Ya.V., Vasylenko N.M., Pilyo S.G., Klyuchko S.V., Brovarets V.S. Screening of Auxin-like Substances among Synthetic Compounds, Derivatives of Pyridine and Pyrimidine. *J Plant Sci Phytopathol*. 2023. 7: 151-156. DOI: 10.29328/journal.jpssp.1001121. <https://www.plantsciencejournal.com/articles/jpssp-aid1121.php>.
24. Tsygankova V.A., Kopich V.M., Voloshchuk I.V., Pilyo S.G., Klyuchko S. V., Brovarets V.S. New growth regulators of barley based on pyrimidine and pyridine derivatives. *Sciences of Europe*. 2023. 124: 13 – 23. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8327852. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8327852>.
25. Tsygankova V.A., Andreev A.M., Andrushevich Ya.V., Pilyo S.G., Brovarets V.S. Effect of plant growth regulators and fertilizers on the vegetative growth of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.). *The scientific heritage*. 2023. Vol.116. No 116. P. 3 – 9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8129039>.
26. Tsygankova V.A., Andreev A.M., Andrushevich Ya.V., Pilyo S.G., Klyuchko S.V., Brovarets V.S. Use Of Synthetic Plant Growth Regulators In Combination With Fertilizers to Improve Wheat Growth. *Int J Med Biotechnol Genetics*. 2023. S1:02:002:9-14. URL: <http://scidoc.org/IJMBGS1V2.php>.
27. Tsygankova V.A., Andrushevich Ya.V., Vasylenko N.M., Kopich V.M., Popilnichenko S.V., Pilyo S.G., Brovarets V.S. Auxin-like and cytokinin-like effects of new synthetic pyrimidine derivatives on the growth and photosynthesis of wheat. *J Plant Sci Phytopathol*. 2024. 8(1): 15–24. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.29328/journal.jpssp.1001126>.
28. Tsygankova V.A., Vasylenko N.M., Andrushevich Ya.V., Kopich V.M., Solomyanni R.M., Pilyo S.G., Bondarenko O.M., Popilnichenko S.V., Brovarets V.S. New Wheat Growth Regulators Based On Thioxopyrimidine Derivatives. *Int J Med Biotechnol Genetics*. 2024; S1:02:004:23-30. <https://scidoc.org/special-issues/IJMBG/S1V2/IJMBG-2379-1020-S1-02-004.pdf>.
29. Tsygankova V.A., Andrushevich Ya.V., Vasylenko N.M., Kopich V.M., Solomyanni R.M., Popilnichenko S.V., Kozachenko O.P., Pilyo S.G., Brovarets V.S. The use of thioxopyrimidine derivatives as new regulators of growth and photosynthesis of barley. *J Plant Sci Phytopathol*. 2024. 8(2): 090-099. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.29328/journal.jpssp.1001139>.
30. Tsygankova V., Andrushevich Ya., Kopich V., Vasylenko N., Solomyanni R., Popilnichenko S., Kachaeva M., Kozachenko O., Pilyo S., & Brovarets V. Wheat growth in the vegetative phase under the regulatory effect of furopyrimidine derivatives. *The scientific heritage*. 2024. 140: 3-12. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12720609.
31. Tsygankova V., Vasylenko N., Andrushevich Ya., Kopich V., Kachaeva M., Popilnichenko S., Kozachenko O., Pilyo S., Brovarets V. Application of thienopyrimidine derivatives as new eco-friendly wheat growth regulators. *Sciences of Europe*. 2024. 146: 8 – 18. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13267799.